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High resolution modelling of the urban heat island of 100 European cities

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ABSTRACT

In urban areas across Europe, high air temperatures and urban heat islands (UHIs) greatly affect public health, with climate change further increasing the mortality risks. This study presents a validated high resolution (100 m) hourly air temperature dataset for 100 European cities for a 10-year period (2008–2017) that is made available for urban climate research. The data is used to analyse the UHI (as defined in this study) of these 100 cities, using a dedicated indicator that is suitable for comparison across Europe. The UHI indicator is found to be correlated to both meteorological and urban characteristics. Using a statistical model, the current and potential cooling of green infrastructure and soil unsealing in the 100 cities is quantified. The Europe-wide current impact of these climate adaptation measures on the UHI indicator is found to range between 0.03 and 1.82 °C (with an average value of 0.45 °C), which is significant compared to the UHI indicator values ranging between 0.57 and 2.54 °C (with an average value of 1.43 °C). Nevertheless, a large potential for extra cooling from such measures is found to remain in many cities, ranging between 0 and 1 °C, with the Europe-wide average value being 0.49 °C, slightly higher than the estimated current cooling.

1. Introduction

Cities generally experience higher air temperatures than their rural surroundings, the so-called urban heat island (UHI) phenomenon, which manifests itself mainly during the evening and the night when air temperature differences at 2 m height can reach up to 10 °C under favourable conditions (Landsberg, 1981; Oke, 1982). The UHI is caused by the increased heat capacity of cities through the development of buildings and impervious surfaces, which traps energy and both short- and longwave radiation (e.g. inside street canyons), and inhibits evaporative cooling (Oke et al., 1991). Furthermore, anthropogenic activities, such as heating and transportation, further increase the amount of heat released in urban areas, compared to the natural landscape (Zhou et al., 2017). Because of the UHI increment, cities are particularly vulnerable to heat waves. As an illustration, in the city of Berlin up to 30% higher heat-related excess mortalities are found compared to the rural areas around the city (Gabriel and Endlicher, 2011). This problem will become more severe in the future because of global climate change and urban population growth in cities (Li et al., 2021).

The extent and distribution of UHI is studied both through air temperature and Land Surface Temperature (LST) data. The latter allows for a spatially explicit analysis of the surface skin temperature, but this is an indirect estimate of the UHI, which differs from 2 m

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air temperatures (Jin and Dickinson, 2010). Generally a positive difference between the surface skin temperature and the air temperature is found during daytime and a negative difference at night, which can be attributed mainly to a quicker response of surface temperatures to solar radiation than air temperatures (Prigent et al., 2003). LST-based UHI studies are increasingly common as this is a cheap and practical analysis which can be performed at regional (e.g. Zhou et al., 2017) or even global scales (e.g. Liu et al., 2022).

A second approach is to directly study the air temperatures in and around cities, ideally using meteorological monitoring stations. These can provide representative and temporally continuous UHI information, although the presence of sufficient weather stations in cities to reach information at 100 m scale is often lacking (Marando et al., 2022). Due to the insufficient coverage of the existing weather stations network for large-scale UHI analysis, also regional and urban climate models with increasingly sophisticated urban parameterizations are used to study the UHI (e.g. Kusaka et al., 2012; McCarthy et al., 2012; Hamdi et al., 2013). But even a model resolution of 1 km is not enough to resolve the most relevant urban-scale features, for which a horizontal spatial resolution of the order of a few 100 m or even higher is required because of the relatively high heterogeneity of the urban land use.

Several studies have analysed the role of meteorological conditions and urban characteristics on the magnitude of the UHI (e.g. Arnfield, 2003; Gedzelman et al., 2003; Lauwaet et al., 2016). The UHI is found to be most pronounced on calm, dry, clear nights during which a strong nocturnal inversion can form over the countryside. There is a strong correlation between the UHI and the cloud cover, wind speed, and near-surface inversion strength. Theeuwes et al. (2017) have developed a diagnostic equation to calculate the daily maximum UHI value based on the sky view factor, vegetation fraction, solar irradiance, mean wind speed and diurnal air temperature range, using data for 14 North-West European cities. van Hove et al. (2015) found the UHI of Rotterdam to be significantly related to building, impervious and green surface fractions, as well as to mean building height.

An important strategy to mitigate UHI and to promote a resilient environment in cities is the deployment of green infrastructure (Saaroni et al., 2018). O'Malley et al. (2015) found green infrastructure (trees, shrubs and grass) to be the most effective in reducing UHI, compared to other measures such as urban inland water bodies and high albedo materials. In a European-wide study by Marando et al. (2022), existing urban green infrastructure is found to cool the average estimated summertime 2 m air temperatures in European cities by 1.07 °C, and up to 2.9 °C. In this context, Tiwari et al. (2021) and Marando et al. (2022) point to the need of high-resolution air temperature datasets at the European scale as well as studies assessing quantitatively the impact of green infrastructure on microclimate regulation in cities.

This paper builds on the research mentioned above by investigating the relationship between the UHI of 100 cities, geographically spread across Europe, and both meteorological and urban characteristics by applying a validated high resolution (100 m) urban climate model. Based on these relations, a simple regression model is built to quantify the current and potential cooling of green infrastructure and soil unsealing, two popular climate adaptation measures in cities. The data on which this paper builds were developed in the framework of the Copernicus Health contract for the C3S data platform (Hooyberghs et al., 2019). The dataset has already been used for a health impact assessment (Jungman et al., 2023). The paper aims to provide scientific added value by:

- presenting a validated high resolution (100 m) hourly air temperature dataset for an unprecedented number of European cities
- working out a European wide comparable UHI indicator that addresses the confounding effects of weather, relief and time on reported UHI magnitudes, which are problematic issues in many UHI studies
- quantifying the current and potential cooling of vegetation cover and soil unsealing in these 100 cities

2. Data and methods

2.1. The UrbClim model

The urban boundary-layer climate model UrbClim (De Ridder et al., 2015) is designed to simulate and study the UHI for agglomeration-scale model domains at a high spatial resolution, taken as 100 m for this study. UrbClim is composed of a land surface scheme containing simplified urban physics, coupled to a 3D atmospheric boundary-layer module. The atmospheric module is tied to synoptic-scale meteorological fields through the lateral and top boundary conditions, to ensure that the synoptic forcing is properly taken into account. The land surface scheme is based on the soil-vegetation-atmosphere transfer scheme of De Ridder and Schayes (1997), which is extended to account for urban surface physics. This is accomplished by representing the urban surface as a rough impermeable slab, with appropriate values for the albedo, emissivity, thermal conductivity and volumetric heat capacity. The main feature of the urbanisation is the inclusion of a parameterization of the inverse Stanton number, which is known to be much higher in urban areas (Kanda et al., 2007; De Ridder et al., 2012). The choice for this parameterization implies that cities (and all other areas) are represented as a bluff-rough surface in the model grid cells, and individual features (e.g. buildings) can not be resolved, limiting the spatial resolution of the model to 100 m at minimum. A full description of the UrbClim model can be found in De Ridder et al. (2015).

The UrbClim model has been subjected to exhaustive validation regarding its energy fluxes, 2 m wind speeds, air temperatures and urban-rural temperature differences for the cities of London, Bilbao, Athens, Toulouse, Berlin, Antwerp, Ghent, Brussels and Barcelona (De Ridder et al., 2015; García-Díez et al., 2016; Lauwaet et al., 2015, 2016, 2020; Zhou et al., 2016). The land surface temperatures of the land surface scheme in UrbClim have been validated with satellite data for the city of London (Zhou et al., 2016). Furthermore, the urban parameterization was tested for the city of Paris, and the simulated land surface temperature compared favourably to observed values obtained from thermal infrared satellite imagery (De Ridder et al., 2012).

2.2. Model set-up

The UrbClim model has been applied at 100 m resolution to provide hourly temperature data for 100 European cities for a 10-year time period (2008–2017). The cities were selected based on user requirements of the stakeholders of the Copernicus Health project, aiming for a high spatial distribution with specific focus on Eastern European countries that often lack access to relevant information. A full list of the modelled cities is provided in Annex A. The simulated model domains vary in size dependent on the width of the city under investigation, but are always chosen such that they comprise the city and its immediate rural surroundings, aiming for a rural boundary of 5 km around the city. To set up the model simulations, two types of input data are required: terrain specific data and meteorological data.

The terrain specific data describe the actual terrain lay-out of every grid cell. First, the spatial distribution of land use types, needed for the specification of required land surface parameters, is taken from the CORINE 2012 land cover dataset. Second, the percentage of urban land cover in each grid cell is attributed according to the Imperviousness 2012 layer from Copernicus Land service. Third, the amount of vegetation in each grid cell is estimated for each month of the year separately, using the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) from Copernicus Land service, which is measured by the PROBA-V satellite. Four, UrbClim requires a digital elevation model to take into account the height effects, which is taken from the GMTED2010 Dataset (Danielson and Gesch, 2011). And finally, the specification of the anthropogenic heat flux, which is the amount of heat produced by the city and its inhabitants (coming from traffic exhaust, heating devices etc.), is taken from the global dataset of Flanner (2009).

Meteorological initial and lateral boundary conditions were obtained from the European Center for Medium-Range Weather Forecast (ECMWF) ERA5 reanalysis. Soil temperature and soil moisture from ERA5 were used to initialise the model, after which they evolved freely, and a two-month spin-up period was applied to ensure model equilibrium between external forcing and internal dynamics. The lateral forcing parameters include surface pressure, rainfall, incoming solar and longwave radiation, wind speed, air temperature, potential temperature, specific humidity and pressure gradient force. Sea surface temperature was prescribed from ERA5 throughout the simulated period inside the model domains.

Fig. 1. Scatter plot of modelled and observed time-average 2 m air temperatures for 67 measurement stations for the period 2008–2017 based on hourly timeseries. Only rural measurement stations were available for this comparison.

2.3. Urban heat island indicator definition

In order to perform a pan-European analysis of the UHI, it is important to use an indicator that is not dependent on local conditions such as the topography or the presence of sea areas in the model domain. Here we opt for the spatial 90th percentile (P90) urban heat island intensity of a given city. This indicator is calculated for a given city by subtracting the rural (non-water) spatial 10th percentile (P10) air temperature value from the time-averaged, height-corrected (to exclude terrain effects) air temperature map based on the entire hourly timeseries; and then taking the P90 value, which is done to exclude the most extreme values and have a representative value for all cities. The rural and urban areas are defined following the CORINE 2012 land use classification, with all artificial surface classes considered urban and all other classes (except for water bodies) considered rural. The terrain height correction is performed by rescaling the temperatures to the average city height, applying a lapse rate of $6.5 \text{ K}\cdot\text{km}^{-1}$ which is commonly used for height corrections (Dutra et al., 2020). This P90 urban heat island intensity is mapped for the summer season only (JJA), following related scientific literature (e.g. Dosio, 2016). This indicator represents the specific exposure of single cities and due to the height correction is comparable across Europe. While many definitions of the UHI already exist in scientific literature, the UHI indicator used in this paper addresses the confounding effects of weather, relief and time on reported UHI magnitudes, which are problematic issues in many UHI studies (Stewart, 2011).

3. Results

3.1. Model output and validation

Similar set-ups of the UrbClim model have already been subjected to validation exercises for a large number of European cities in the past, but an additional comparison to measurement data is performed for the simulations reported in this study. Therefore all available measurement stations from the Global Surface Summary of the Day produced by the National Climatic Data Center (NCDC) within the 100 model domains are selected that have a data availability of over 90% for hourly air temperatures in the period 2008–2017. The hourly air temperatures of the 67 selected measurement stations that fulfilled the requirements are compared to the simulated air temperatures of the model grid cells with a matching land cover classification that are located closest to the measurement

Fig. 2. Hourly box plots of observed (light grey) and modelled (white) time-average 2 m air temperatures (T2M) for the 67 measurement stations for the period 2008–2017 based on hourly timeseries. The box plots show the minimum, lower quartile, median, upper quartile, and maximum values.

stations. Fig. 1 shows a comparison of the 10-year time average 2 m air temperatures for these stations.

There is a good correspondence between the modelled and measurement data, as the model has on average a small positive bias of 0.4 °C, a root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.77 °C and a high correlation coefficient (CORR) of 0.97. Furthermore, also the complete hourly time series of these 67 measurement stations are compared to the modelled time series, with resulting average error statistics: a bias of 0.4 °C, a root mean square of 2.03 °C and a correlation coefficient of 0.97. Fig. 2 compares the 10-year time average daily cycle between the model and the observations, showing a good overall correspondence, except for a slight overestimation of the night-time and early morning temperatures. The validation numbers reported here are in line with previous validation experiments (De Ridder et al., 2015; García-Díez et al., 2016; Lauwaet et al., 2015, 2016, 2020; Zhou et al., 2016) and demonstrate the capability of the UrbClim model to reproduce observed air temperatures for different locations all over Europe.

The primary output of the model consists of hourly data of the air temperature at 2 m height with a spatial resolution of 100 m. As an example, Fig. 3 shows the 10-year average air temperature map for Barcelona (Spain) for the summer period (JJA). This map demonstrates the spatial variation of air temperatures in and around a city, with the highest temperatures in the city center and decreasing temperatures towards the outskirts of the city. Large green areas in the city are visible as ‘cool islands’. Also the topography is clearly visible from the map. Note that the map shows the average situation and that the temperature differences between the city and the rural surroundings are highly variable over time, depending on cloudiness, wind speed and direction, time of the day, etc.

Based on these maps and after performing the terrain height correction, the UHI indicator is calculated for all 100 cities included in the project. Fig. 4 shows the spatial distribution of the UHI indicator across Europe. The specific value for each city is included in Annex A. A slight north-south and west-east gradient is visible in the figure, with a cluster of high UHI indicator values in the south-east of Europe. A more detailed analysis on the factors determining the UHI indicator is presented in Section 3.2.

3.2. Factors determining the urban heat island strength

In order to perform a deeper analysis of the urban heat island indicator results that are presented in Fig. 4 and Annex A, the indicator values are compared to a number of potential explanatory factors that are reported in previous studies and are useful for a

Fig. 3. Mean 2 m air temperature [°C] in Barcelona (Spain) for JJA of the years 2008–2017 based on hourly timeseries.

Fig. 4. Spatial distribution of the UHI indicator for all 100 modelled cities in Europe. These values are based on 10-year averages (2008–2017) for the summer period (JJA).

Europe-wide analysis (e.g. [van Hove et al., 2015](#); [Lauwaet et al., 2016](#)): the average wind speed, downward solar radiation, vegetation cover, soil sealing, the total population and the population density of a given city. The average wind speed is calculated by taking the model domain average 10 m wind speed of the UrbClim model for the summer months (June–August). The average downward solar (shortwave) radiation for the summer months is calculated from the ERA5 input data of the model. The vegetation cover value for a given city is calculated from the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) values of the summer months for urban type grid cells. The soil sealing value is determined based on the average imperviousness of urban type grid cells. The total population and population density numbers are derived from the Global Human Settlement layer population grid map of 2015. For the total population, the sum of the population within the model domain of a city is calculated and then log transformed to improve linearity between the variables, whereas the population density is calculated by dividing the total population by the number of urban type grid cells. [Fig. 5](#) presents the relation between the UHI indicator and the selected explaining variables, in a descending order of correlation strength. All variables are found to be significantly correlated (with significance level 0.05) with the UHI indicator, with the average wind speed and soil sealing showing the strongest correlation.

3.3. Assessing current and potential cooling from vegetation and soil unsealing in urban grid cells

As a lot of European cities are interested to mitigate their urban heat island, the correlations found above can help to assess how much a given city can realistically reduce the UHI indicator with two very popular climate adaptation measures: greening and soil unsealing. To that purpose, a multiple linear regression model to predict the UHI indicator is fit to the data, including all the explaining variables from [Fig. 4](#):

$$UHI\ P90 = -0.79 - 2.73 \times WS^{0.25} + 2.58 \times SOIL + 0.008 \times DENS + 0.54 \times SW^{0.25} - 0.37 \times VEG + 0.40 \times INH$$

with WS the mean 10 m wind speed during the summer months (m/s), SOIL the mean soil sealing in urban grid cells (%), DENS the population density (number of persons/ha), SW the summer (JJA) mean downward shortwave radiation averaged over the 24 h of a day (W/m^2), VEG the mean vegetation cover in urban grid cells (%) and INH the logarithm of the total population (number of persons). Note that both the wind speed and shortwave radiation variables are transformed to the power of 0.25, following [Theeuwes et al.](#)

Fig. 5. Modelled relation between the UHI indicator and the 6 selected explaining variables. The black lines represent the linear best fit to the data. All correlation coefficients are statistically significant (with significance level 0.05).

Fig. 6. Comparison between the original modelled UHI indicator values and the regression model outcomes. The black line represents the linear best fit to the data.

(caption on next page)

Fig. 7. Estimated current cooling from vegetation and soil unsealing in urban grid cells (upper panel) and estimated potential cooling from vegetation and soil unsealing in urban grid cells (lower panel).

(2017), as this yielded a slightly better overall correlation of the model.

The chi-square value of the regression is 8.58, which is close to a probability of 0.1 for the degrees of freedom of the model. Fig. 6 shows the results of the regression model, compared to the original UHI indicator. The regression model is reasonably capable of reproducing the UHI indicator values based on the explaining variables, with a correlation coefficient of 0.74, although there is some spread in the results and the highest UHI values are a bit underestimated while the lowest UHI values are a bit overestimated.

Of the 6 explaining variables, 4 are beyond the control of city authorities: mean wind speed, solar radiation and the population density and sum. But they can control the mean soil sealing and vegetation cover in urban areas with targeted planning and legislation. So by changing the value for these two variables in the regression model, we can assess how much a city can cool, or is already cooled today, by vegetation and soil unsealing, given their external circumstances. We have limited the maximum and minimum amounts of vegetation cover and soil sealing in urban grid cells to respectively 0.7 and 0.3, which are realistic boundaries given the values currently observed in the 100 cities (Fig. 5). The current cooling from vegetation and soil unsealing is estimated by comparing the actual UHI value of a given city to the value from the regression model when applying a vegetation cover of 0.3 and a soil sealing fraction of 0.7. To estimate the potential cooling from vegetation and soil sealing, the actual UHI value of a given city is compared to the value from the regression model when applying a vegetation cover of 0.7 and a soil sealing fraction of 0.3.

The top panel of Fig. 7 shows a map of the estimated current cooling from vegetation and soil unsealing for the 100 European cities. There is no clear geographical trend visible from the Figure, with higher and lower values spread across Europe. The specific value for each city is included in Annex A, with values ranging from 0.03 °C in Warsaw (Poland) to 1.24 °C in Podgorica (Montenegro). On average the current cooling is estimated at 0.45 °C, which is a significant number given the average UHI indicator value being 1.43 °C. So nowadays a lot of cities are already substantially cooled by vegetation and soil unsealing measures.

Nevertheless, a large potential for extra cooling from such measures remains in many cities, as indicated in the lower panel of Fig. 7 and Annex A. The values range from almost 0 in Stockholm (Sweden) to 0.96 in Bucharest (Romania). The average value over all 100 cities of 0.49 °C is slightly higher than the current cooling value, so there remains a lot of potential for UHI reduction with easily applicable adaptation measures in many cities.

4. Discussion and conclusion

In this paper, the high resolution (100 m) urban climate model UrbClim was applied to simulate the UHI of 100 cities, geographically spread across Europe, over a 10-year time period (2008–2017). UrbClim consists of a sophisticated soil-vegetation-atmosphere transfer scheme that accounts for urban physics, coupled to a simple 3D atmospheric boundary layer model, allowing very fast simulations of entire urban agglomerations over long time periods (De Ridder et al., 2015). Obviously, this speed of execution comes at a price. In particular, the omission of the calculation of the pressure gradient as a function of internal variables inhibits the development of local thermal circulations, in particular the city breeze. Likewise, other thermal circulation systems such as the sea breeze, and anabatic and katabatic winds, cannot be simulated by UrbClim. However, a large number of validation exercises, also for complex terrains and coastal cities, did not reveal particular shortcomings in the model results, as the model was capable of reproducing observed quantities (surface energy fluxes, wind speed, air temperature) as well as any full mesoscale model containing urban surface physics (e.g. De Ridder et al., 2015; García-Díez et al., 2016). These type of mesoscale models are now starting to navigate towards spatial resolutions in the same order as UrbClim (e.g. Ronda et al., 2017; Leroyer et al., 2022), but a study on the scale of ours (both regarding the number of cities as well as the time period) is computationally not possible yet.

The 2 m air temperature data generated with UrbClim were compared to measurements from 67 available meteorological stations, yielding error statistics that were in line with previous validation studies. The urban heat island effect of the cities was analysed through an UHI indicator focussing on the summer months (JJA) that included correction for topographical effects and is comparable across Europe. The results showed a slight north-south and west-east gradient of the UHI indicator across Europe. In general, the UHI numbers are relatively low (between 0.57 and 2.54 °C) when compared to UHI values in other studies (e.g. Zhou et al., 2017) as we are looking at 10-year average air temperature values, the spatial 90th percentile value of the UHI maps, and correcting for topographic effects. The choice to use the spatial 10th and 90th percentiles to calculate the UHI indicator was made after a comparison to other values (P95, P99). This did not significantly change the ranking between cities (and thus the results of the analyses) but it did lead to overall larger values, and a few outlier values in some of the smallest cities. These do not show up in the P90 results, which take a larger number of grid cells into account, leading to a more robust and representative value for the UHI of a given city.

The relationship between the UHI indicator and both meteorological and urban characteristics was investigated, showing significant correlation with 6 selected explaining variables: the average wind speed, downward solar radiation, vegetation cover, soil sealing, the total population and the population density of a given city. This is in line with previous research, as observational studies of e.g. Giannaros and Melas (2012) and van Hove et al. (2015) also found strong correlations between UHI strength and respectively wind speeds and surface imperviousness. Also the positive correlations of UHI with total population and shortwave radiation indicators have been reported before (e.g. Lauwaet et al., 2016; Lauwaet et al., 2018). A negative correlation between UHI and vegetation cover was found, but it is less strong than could perhaps be expected based on outcomes of previous studies (Saaroni et al., 2018; Marando et al., 2022), in which vegetation cover is put forward as very impactful in mitigating the urban heat island. It should be noted that in these studies mainly the local effect of parks and large forests close to the city were investigated, while here we look at vegetation fractions in

urban grid cells, so within the build-up areas. This was found to have a significantly higher correlation to our UHI indicator (the P90 UHI value) than the total amount of vegetation in and around a given city, which had a correlation coefficient of only -0.11 . It shows the need for very local green measures to mitigate the UHI at a given location, as large offsite cooling effects of vegetation are not found in our results, which is confirmed by observational studies (e.g. [Chen et al., 2009](#)).

Based on the selected variables, a multiple linear regression model was set up to assess the cooling potential of green infrastructure and soil unsealing. Values were found to differ significantly across the cities, with no clear geographical pattern. The Europe-wide average current impact of these measures on the UHI indicator was found to be 0.45 °C, a significant value compared to the average P90 UHI value of 1.43 °C over all 100 cities. However, a large potential for extra cooling from such measures was found to remain in many cities, with the Europe-wide average value being 0.49 °C, slightly higher than the estimated current cooling. Note that these values are based on a simple regression model and should be seen as a first order estimate of potential impacts, rather than a precise number for a given city.

The impact values reported here are rather low in comparison to other studies (e.g. [Marando et al., 2022](#)), but these studies mainly focussed on the local cooling effect of vegetation or trees, while here we look at city-wide cooling effects which impact the overall UHI indicator of a city (which does not include the most extreme values and is height-corrected). Studies based on observations have come up with alternative regression models to calculate (maximum) UHI (e.g. [Brandsma and Wolters, 2012](#); [Theeuwes et al., 2017](#); [Leconte et al., 2020](#)). In these studies similar variables are found to define the local UHI at street level or district scale (vegetation fraction, fraction of build-up area, mean wind speed, solar irradiance), but also more local variables as the sky view factor, which could not be taken into account in our study.

Our work adds to the previously gained understanding of how the UHI of European cities is defined and how it compares across the continent, delivering a validated high resolution (100 m) air temperature dataset for 100 cities that was developed in the framework of the Copernicus Health contract for the C3S data platform. Overall, the results of this study were found to be in line with related research studies, and showed the need for very local green measures to mitigate the UHI at a given location, as large offsite cooling effects of vegetation were not found.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Dirk Lauwaet: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Julie Berckmans:** Validation, Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hans Hooyberghs:** Methodology, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hendrik Wouters:** Methodology, Data curation. **Guy Driesen:** Software, Data curation. **Filip Lefebvre:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Koen De Ridder:** Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A

City	Longitude	Latitude	UHI P90 [°C]	Current cooling [°C]	Cooling potential [°C]
Alicante	-0.48	38.36	1.07	0.58	0.28
Amsterdam	4.90	52.36	1.45	0.56	0.78
Antwerp	4.40	51.25	1.24	0.52	0.37
Athens	23.73	37.98	2.10	0.41	0.78
Barcelona	2.13	41.38	1.37	0.23	0.63
Bari	16.84	41.12	0.72	0.47	0.23
Basel	7.59	47.56	1.46	0.32	0.45

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City	Longitude	Latitude	UHI P90 [°C]	Current cooling [°C]	Cooling potential [°C]
Belgrado	20.40	44.81	1.48	0.68	0.31
Berlin	13.41	52.52	1.73	0.53	0.55
Bilbao	-2.94	43.29	0.95	0.50	0.35
Birmingham	-1.89	52.48	1.17	0.49	0.43
Bologna	11.34	44.50	1.54	0.58	0.34
Bordeaux	-0.59	44.83	1.52	0.38	0.38
Brasov	25.60	45.66	2.13	0.19	0.81
Bratislava	17.11	48.14	1.39	0.40	0.57
Brussels	4.37	50.84	1.50	1.07	0.28
Bucharest	26.09	44.45	2.22	0.03	0.96
Budapest	19.13	47.50	1.99	0.04	0.85
Charleroi	4.44	50.42	1.16	0.72	0.27
Cluj_Napoca	23.61	46.78	2.11	0.63	0.70
Cologne	6.96	50.95	1.40	0.13	0.63
Copenhagen	12.55	55.67	0.81	0.15	0.57
Debrecen	21.62	47.52	1.50	0.23	0.64
Dublin	-6.26	53.33	0.99	0.53	0.34
Dusseldorf	6.81	51.23	1.29	0.15	0.59
Edinburgh	-3.21	55.95	0.77	0.71	0.26
Frankfurt_am_Main	8.66	50.11	1.45	0.12	0.62
Gdansk	18.63	54.38	0.87	0.28	0.50
Geneva	6.13	46.21	1.33	0.66	0.21
Genoa	8.89	44.43	0.87	0.37	0.31
Ghent	3.72	51.08	1.04	0.65	0.19
Glasgow	-4.25	55.85	0.98	0.44	0.30
Goteborg	11.98	57.71	0.75	0.68	0.11
Graz	15.44	47.05	1.60	0.76	0.13
Gyor	17.66	47.69	1.75	0.45	0.74
Hamburg	9.99	53.54	1.46	0.09	0.71
Helsinki	24.94	60.21	1.05	0.41	0.37
Klaipeda	21.16	55.71	1.22	0.35	0.83
Kosice	21.26	48.71	1.29	0.36	0.43
Krakow	19.96	50.05	1.49	0.68	0.34
Leeds	-1.55	53.80	0.79	0.43	0.37
Leipzig	12.36	51.34	1.42	0.33	0.53
Liege	5.58	50.64	1.20	0.98	0.12
Lille	3.06	50.63	1.40	0.55	0.56
Lisbon	-9.14	38.70	1.11	0.08	0.64
Ljubljana	14.51	46.06	1.47	0.44	0.32
Lodz	19.46	51.76	1.21	0.70	0.32
London	-0.13	51.51	1.47	0.42	0.60
Luxembourg	6.13	49.61	1.17	0.52	0.46
Lyon	4.83	45.76	2.18	0.29	0.76
Madrid	-3.70	40.41	1.72	0.40	0.50
Malaga	-4.42	36.72	1.27	0.26	0.48
Marseille	5.43	43.30	1.24	0.40	0.64
Milan	9.19	45.46	2.01	0.13	0.75
Miskolc	20.75	48.10	1.77	0.29	0.69
Montpellier	3.88	43.62	1.27	0.49	0.42
Munich	11.55	48.16	1.81	0.13	0.71
Murcia	-1.13	37.99	1.31	0.73	0.22
Nantes	-1.55	47.23	1.22	0.40	0.47
Naples	14.26	40.85	1.74	0.12	0.82
Newcastle	-1.60	54.97	0.90	0.24	0.45
Nice	7.26	43.71	1.46	0.63	0.24
Novi_Sad	19.84	45.27	2.14	0.71	0.73
Oslo	10.75	59.89	0.73	0.49	0.07
Padua	11.88	45.42	2.13	0.91	0.38
Palermo	13.35	38.13	0.98	0.58	0.18
Palma_de_Mallorca	2.65	39.57	0.72	0.51	0.14
Paris	2.35	48.86	2.12	0.15	0.95
Pecs	18.24	46.08	1.21	0.29	0.46
Podgorica	19.26	42.42	2.16	1.24	0.00
Porto	-8.56	41.18	1.25	0.15	0.52
Prague	14.42	50.06	1.71	0.23	0.71
Reykjavik	-21.83	64.12	0.98	0.28	0.41
Riga	24.12	56.97	1.06	0.36	0.45
Rome	12.48	41.86	1.89	0.54	0.51
Rotterdam	4.45	51.90	1.66	0.33	0.85
Sarajevo	18.36	43.85	1.32	0.47	0.28

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City	Longitude	Latitude	UHI P90 [°C]	Current cooling [°C]	Cooling potential [°C]
Sevilla	-5.98	37.39	1.46	0.26	0.53
Skopje	21.43	42.00	1.75	0.48	0.46
Sofia	23.33	42.69	2.22	0.19	0.75
Split	16.46	43.51	1.40	0.21	0.73
Stockholm	18.07	59.33	0.57	0.74	0.00
Strasbourg	7.74	48.58	1.83	0.33	0.61
Szeged	20.15	46.26	1.60	0.76	0.39
Tallinn	24.76	59.43	1.08	0.34	0.49
Tartu	26.73	58.37	1.15	0.60	0.50
Thessaloniki	22.95	40.63	1.69	0.19	0.65
Tirana	19.79	41.34	2.54	1.04	0.08
Toulouse	1.43	43.59	1.35	0.31	0.46
Trieste	13.79	45.64	1.14	0.66	0.28
Turin	7.68	45.07	2.42	0.10	0.86
Utrecht	5.08	52.09	1.45	1.07	0.57
Valencia	-0.39	39.48	1.34	0.21	0.58
Varna	27.93	43.21	1.73	0.21	1.00
Vienna	16.41	48.20	1.66	0.48	0.63
Vilnius	25.28	54.68	1.12	0.22	0.53
Warsaw	21.05	52.23	1.70	0.03	0.81
Wroclaw	17.03	51.10	1.29	0.70	0.33
Zagreb	15.97	45.83	1.38	0.41	0.33
Zurich	8.53	47.39	1.45	0.62	0.18
Average values			1.43	0.45	0.49

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